

REQUIREMENTS FOR ENSURING PRODUCT QUALITY INDICATORS

Khudoyberdiyeva Nilufar Shavkatovna

Rashidova Gulasalkhon Nodirovna

Bukhara engineering technology institute

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Abstract. *At all stages of human development, the concept of “quality” is special approach, different definitions are given to it, but the essence is exactly the same It is understood that the thing satisfies the specified need.*

Keywords: *evaluates, characteristic, product, ehrams, enterprises, requirements, methods, checklists.*

ТРЕБОВАНИЯ К ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЮ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ КАЧЕСТВА ПРОДУКЦИИ

Аннотация. *На всех этапах развития человека к понятию «качество» относится особый подход, ему даются разные определения, но суть совершенно одна и та же. Подразумевается, что вещь удовлетворяет указанную потребность.*

Ключевые слова: *оценивает, характеристика, продукт, предприятия, требования, методы, контрольные листы.*

The ancient thinker Aristotle defined quality in various aspects of human activity imagined in the form of a set of qualities of achievable results. American industrialist Henry Ford evaluates quality in this way “Quality is nobody is to do everything well even if you don't see it”.

Product quality is the result of the function of the product, its specific consumption is a set of features that show its suitability to meet the requirements. Indicators of product quality - product creation, use and consumption one or more related to its quality related to certain conditions of making is a quantitative characteristic of its properties. Product quality management is during product creation, operation keeping the quality indicators at the required level in the process of making or consumption is a movement to stand up.

Quality control - is optimal during the design and construction phase ensuring the level, modern scientific and technical capabilities and customer requirements matching, and then in the production process, these quality indicators are realistic means providing the product. State standardization system product serves as the main factor of quality management.

Product technology - in production, consumption and repair compatibility of the composition and structure to achieve the optimal cost of resources a complex feature of a characterizing product.

The safety of the product is a measure of the harmful effect on a person complex nature of the product. Determining, ensuring and maintaining product quality at the required level through the actions taken in its creation and consumption product quality can be controlled. Quality management international internationally recognized systems are ISO 9000, ISO 14000 and other systems can be displayed.

Quality control is a mandatory part of any production in the process, finished products aimed at identifying a marriage or defects and its production testing process. Quality control techniques test materials and raw materials starting with raw materials and checking the conformity of finished product characteristics used at all stages of production.

Such a process includes product testing of finished individual parts. Internal inspection of a specific enterprise is carried out by the Central Service of Quality Assurance is increased. These supervisory tasks include:

- development of quality indicators for each product;
- methods of acceptance of quality control and test procedures;
- detailed analysis;
- possible causes of defects and measures to eliminate them determination.

Quality control, as well as production and service includes a review of the technological process used. As mentioned above, this is necessary to implement quality control.

If so, checklists are used in the production process. The whole process information about them is stored in them. The choice of such products, its manufacturer related to the type and purpose of release. Briefly speaking about the quality of the product, we emphasize that for the consumer, the product is reliable, aesthetically attractive and performs its tasks it will be of high quality if it is performed continuously. These depend on the quality indicators of the product.

With the emergence of human society, "the establishment of rules and there was a demand for the emergence of "application". Writing, counting system, monetary unit, different units of measurement - all these are the first shoots of standardization. As production progressed, standardization also progressed. And this influenced the rapid growth of production forces, In ancient Rome, water fountains were made of pipes of exactly the same diameter was It is correct that the treated stones should be of specific (standard) sizes made it possible to build Egyptian ehrsams with a geometric shape. One of the Ehrsams stones weighing several tons are so accurately worked and densely packed together laid so that even a needle does not pass between them. 90 m high Babylon 85 million in the construction of the tower. This is evidenced by the fact that single standard bricks were used shows that there were certain rules and procedures in brick baking.

Standardization is repetitive in science, technology and economics to find a solution to the problems and arrange them at a favorable level in a certain area is a referral activity. There are many standards and serial production determined for the most important products to be released. Machine in standards, tools, weapons, various materials and types, types, models, shapes, sizes, in relation to them technical requirements, as well as test methods, placement and storage, en route transportation rules are defined. Standard units of measurement, designations, practical technical terms and definitions are also shown, without which the quality of the product cannot be clearly defined. Each standard has a number and a year of approval. For example, the 1962 Standard on Basic Definitions of Permissibility and Transfers if approved, it is defined as follows: GOST 7713-62. Here GOST — State standard, the four digits on the left (7713) are the serial number of the standard, the last two and the number (62) indicates the year of approval of the standard. The main purpose of standardization is: science and technology acceleration of development, society's production and labor productivity increase, improve product quality and ensure its acceptable level, people improvement of management of the economy and approval of the produced product establishment of nomenclature, product design and production development of specialization, as well as rationalization of production funds use, saving material and labor resources, health and labor ensuring security, international economic, technical and cultural cooperation development.

On standardization to achieve these goals activities should be focused on solving the following issues:

--- Based on comprehensive standardization of finished product quality final products, raw materials, materials, semi-finished products and components setting requirements for product quality characteristics.

--- System of uniform indicators of product quality, its test and control methods and tools and product requirements taking into account the level of reliability, its nature and conditions of use development with.

--- Ensuring convenient product quality and types of models and sizes product design in order to eliminate the redundancy of variety and establishing standard requirements and methods in production.

--- Production specialization, complex production processes mechanization and automation, interchangeability It is important to raise the level, use and repair the product effectively development of industrial product unification as a condition.

--- Ensuring the unit of measurement and accuracy in the country, high accuracy improvement of measuring methods and tools.

--- Unified system of documents and important fields of science and technology establishing uniform terms and definitions,

--- Labor safety, nature protection and use of natural resources establishing systems of standards in the field of improvement.

Standardization is the production of a certain material in the near future ensures development and all enterprises improve the quality of their products forces to raise the level.

We use a lot of things (tools, devices, machines), cars, etc. in life, construction and technology. The work during this period, these items fail, wear out, and become unusable.

Therefore, in order to re-use items, repair them, that is, it is necessary to replace their broken parts with new ones. Only if the dimensions of the replacement part are correct, it will fit into the product, otherwise, you will have to resize that part. That's it it can be concluded that the repair work of the broken parts of the products sizes that are known and enforced for ease of use production is necessary. This system of dimensions is called standardization.

The most important importance of standardization is that it has a necessary effect on the rate and level of development of production. Of this and for the standardization of science and technology and practical experiences relies on achievements. Hence, the importance of standardization is that ease and convenience in replacing broken parts with another is to create.

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